

Research

Open Reduction & Internal Fixation of Anterior Mandibular Fracture by Double Y Shaped Miniplate vs Conventional Double Miniplate: A Comparative Study

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Abstract: This Quasi-experimental Study was performed to evaluate the efficacy of a double Y-shaped miniplate vs a conventional double miniplate as a treatment modality for the management of simple anterior mandibular fracture. A total of 40 participants with anterior mandibular (symphysis & para symphysis) fractures indicated for open reduction and internal fixation were selected and grouped into as follows: one double Y-shaped miniplate fixed by 6 screws for group I and 2 conventional mini plates fixed by 8 to 10 screws for group II. Participants were evaluated preoperatively, intra-operatively, and postoperatively for the assessment of occlusion, stability of fracture, maximum mouth opening, operating time, postoperative complications, and radiographically bone healing at 1st week, 1st month, and 3rd month. The results revealed that all simple anterior mandibular fractures went to good bone union after surgery. The mean operating time for a double Y-shaped miniplate was less compared to a conventional double miniplate (due to its configuration, easy adaptation, and less screw) which was statistically significant. Postoperative orthopantomogram showed adequate reduction and bone healing on fracture lines in both groups. The postoperative occlusion, stability, and postsurgical complication were statistically insignificant. It was found that double Y-shaped mini plates have the same stabilization due to their configuration as conventional mini plates in fixation of simple anterior mandibular fractures but the use of Double Y-shaped mini plates is less invasive, less time-consuming, and has less complication than conventional mini plates. It leads to good rigidity & stability without permanent neuro-sensory deficit. It is concluded that a double Y-shaped miniplate could be used as an alternative to conventional mini plates in simple anterior mandibular fractures.

Keywords: Mandible fracture, Open reduction, Internal fixation, double Y shaped miniplate, conventional double miniplate

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Introduction

The mandible is a unique bone having a complex role in aesthetics of the face and functional occlusion. Because of the prominent position of the lower jaw, mandibular fractures are the most common fractures of the facial skeleton. It has been reported that fractures of the mandible account for 36% to 59% of all maxillofacial fracture.¹ Mandibular fracture constitute the bulk of the trauma treated by oral and maxillofacial services.² Esthetic and functional disability brings morbidity to the trauma patient and is of primary concern to the maxillofacial surgeon. The aim of all forms of the therapy is restoration of the form and function of the face and jaws to near normal.³

Mandible is the second most commonly fractured bone in the maxillofacial region because of its prominence and position.⁴ A study was conducted in Bangladesh reported that fractures occur at various locations like body, angle, condyle, coronoid, ramus and dentoalveolar region. The incidence of mandible fracture according to anatomic distributions are in body-30.2%, symphysis-25.3%, parasymphysis-25.3%, angle-18.5%.⁵ In Bangladesh, Amin et al.² and Sultana et al.⁶ 2018 in their study showed that the most common site of mandible fracture is parasymphysis which accounts approximately 26% to 40% of all mandibular fracture. However there is wide variance in the reported percentage of fractures of the mandible that occur in the anterior mandible, studies done in Kenya, Nigeria, Egypt, Canada and India places this at approximately 23% to 36% of all mandibular fractures.⁴

Anterior mandibular fractures (AMFs) are defined as mandibular fractures that involve a region bounded bilaterally by vertical lines just distal to the canine teeth (the parasymphysis) or linear fractures that run in the midline of the mandible (symphysis).⁷ The history of treatment of facial bone fractures parallels the development in modern oral and maxillofacial surgery. If put on the time line the management of trauma has evolved greatly over the years from supportive bandages, splints, circummandibular wiring, extraoral pin to rigid fixation and more lately semi rigid fixation.³

Management of fractures of the mandible represents an important clinical challenge. The goal of management of mandibular fracture is the restoration of anatomic form, function, re-establishment of occlusion, functional and facial aesthetics. The close reduction technique is noncompliance for many patients due to prolonged restricted mouth opening, difficulty to maintain nutrition and oral hygiene, communication problem, social embarrassment, in case of children chances of ankylosis etc.⁸

The technique of rigid internal fixation by compression plate was developed and popularized by the study of internal fixation (AO/ASIF) in Europe in 1970s. The compression plate rigidly fixed the fractured bony segments sufficiently to prevent inter-fragmentary movement and provide healing by primary intention.⁹ However, despite of having these advantages the rigid internal fixation has been criticized for having increased morbidity, difficulty of procedure, increased operating time, cost of equipment, necessity of prolonged hospital stay, bulk of the plate, scar formation due to extraoral approach and increase chance of nerve injury were their disadvantages.¹⁰

Treatment of mandible fractures has changed over the last 20 years. In recent years, there has been a trend towards rigid fixation with miniplates as the postoperative results were satisfactory. This has helped to reduce malocclusion, non-union, improved mouth opening, speech, oral hygiene, decrease loss and the ability for patients to return to work earlier.⁶ With the advent of internal fixation techniques come the opportunity to obtain both the re-establishment of the patient's normal occlusion and anatomical bony reduction.¹¹

Internal fixation of mandibular fractures with miniplates (in conformity with the tension band principle), Champy et al.³ advised the use of two miniplates in the anterior region, one at the inferior border and the second 5 mm above the lower plate. Champy's principle is still followed.⁷

Transorally placed miniplates have gained wide acceptance for the treatment of mandibular fractures as described by Champy et al.³ Recently various modifications in transorally placed miniplates for direct fixation of mandibular fracture are gaining popularity. The modifications have various advantages like more rigidity, less foreign materials, less time in application etc. Among the various modifications of miniplates, three dimensional (3-D) plating system is also gaining popularity.¹²

The use of 3-dimensional (3D) plates system has been one of the methods of fixation of mandibular fractures challenging the Champy technique for the fixation.¹³ There is a simultaneous stabilization of the tension and compression zones, making 3D plates a time saving alternative to conventional miniplates. As same as in 3D plate system, shaped plate as double Y shaped plate consider as one mini plate either than use of two plates in fixation, with save of compression and tension load, double y shaped mini plates should as most plate stable under load in mandibular fracture.⁴

Single and double Y-shaped miniplates demonstrated the highest biomechanical stability and provided significantly greater resistance to displacement and Y-shaped miniplates allow larger area coverage with more holes and screws, and this advantage provides the effect of double miniplates through a single construct. Additionally, Y-shaped miniplates prevent the rotational movements of immobilized fractured segments.¹⁴ As the double Y shaped mini plate is a single plate, less screws are used in fixation (six screws) compared to using two conventional plates which will consume between eight to ten screws, hence increasing the time spent to adapt the plates and complete fixation. It is a significantly faster fixation time compared to conventional miniplates used in the study.⁴ However, the usage of double Y shaped miniplate for the treatment of anterior mandibular fracture is needed to be justified. This study was therefore planned with the aim to evaluate the efficacy of double y shaped miniplate over conventional double miniplate taking certain parameter of success into consideration i.e – stability after fixation between two techniques, to determine the operating time and to assay postoperative complications between two techniques

Research Methodology

This Quasi experimental Study was performed at the Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery, Dhaka Dental College Hospital, Mirpur-14, Dhaka during the period of From July, 2017 to June, 2018. Participants who attend to the Department of Oral & Maxillofacial Surgery, Dhaka Dental College & Hospital as a diagnosed case of anterior mandibular (symphysis & parasymphysis) fracture by clinically & radiologically were included in this study. Participants with recent simple anterior mandibular fracture, Unilateral fracture, age between 18 to 60 years were included in this study.

Procedure

The participants were randomly divided into two equal groups according to the type of hardware used for fracture fixation. Group I– (20 Patients) was treated using double Y shaped miniplate and Group II– (20 patients) was treated using conventional double miniplate. All surgical procedure was performed under general anesthesia. Erich arch bars was first applied to the both upper and lower jaw. Intraoral vestibular incision was made for anterior mandibular

fracture reduction. Vestibular incision site and surgical field was infiltrated with 2% Lignocaine hydrochloride with Epinephrine solution. Then a lower vestibular incision was given to expose fracture site according to need without damage mental nerve. Mucoperiosteal flap was elevated to expose the fracture site. Once the fracture had been reduced to the anatomical position, temporary maxillomandibular fixation (MMF) was given. After that in case of group I fixation was done by using one 2.0 mm double Y-shaped six holes with 9mm spacing miniplate. Use of monocortical mini-screws 9 mm in the lower part of the double Y-shaped miniplate. Use of monocortical 7 mm mini-screws in the upper border of the double Y-shaped miniplate. Release of intermaxillary fixation and reevaluation of occlusion was done. After proper irrigation and adequate hemostasis closure of the wounds was done in layers. Estimation of the operation time. In case of group II, fixation was done by two conventional miniplates. The lower plate was fix first at the level of lower border and followed by upper plate about 5mm above the lower plate at the subapical region.

A pressure dressing was applied to the submental region to prevent postoperative hematoma formation. The patient was maintained on a soft diet for two weeks. All surgeries were performed under proper antibiotic coverage.

Postoperative clinical evaluation was done at the 1st day, 1st week & 1st month, 3rd month respectively. Radiological evaluation was also done at immediate postoperatively & 1st month, 3rd month respectively. Evaluations of Preoperative Assessment such as Associated fractures of the mandible, Preoperative occlusion, Presence of teeth in the fracture line, Any paresthesia or anesthesia of involved area. Radiographic examination was done to confirm the clinical findings, determine the degree and direction of displacement of the fracture segment and locate the fracture line.

Postoperative Assessment included the assessment of occlusion was checked clinically, to know if there was any step in the occlusal plane, gap in the occlusal plane while teeth in occlusion as 1 point: Derangement of occlusion (All the teeth in either of fracture fragments were out of occlusion), 2 points: Mild occlusal discrepancy (only few teeth in either of the fracture fragments or both fragments were out of occlusion), and 3 points: occlusion the same as before injury. The Assessment of stability of fractures (By manipulation of segments) was performed by 1 point: Mobility present, 2 points: Mobility absent. The Evaluation of complications by surgeons as rated as 1 points: Present, 2 points: Absent. Maximum mouth opening was scored as 1 point : < 30 mm, 2 point : 30-39 mm, 3 points : >40mm. Furthermore, the duration of complete surgical procedure was also evaluated. Finally, The participants was radiographically assessed immediate postoperatively and then 1st month, 3rd month post-operatively by orthopantomogram. It assessed the adequacy of reduction of the fractured segments, and the fracture healing progression.

Data collection and analysis

A standardized structured data collection sheet (Appendix-A) was used to collect necessary information of the subject group. Data sheet included all of the variables regarding to the study. Data were to be stored and analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Scientist (SPSS version 22, Chicago Inc.). Data were entered in to template of SPSS software. Demographic characteristics were expressed as frequency using tabular and graphical pattern. Assessment of occlusion, stability, maximum mouth opening, operating time, cost of fixation material and postsurgical complications were reported. Level of significance was tested using chi-square and unpaired t-test for categorical variables and analysis of variant.

Result

The age ranged from 18-60 years and mean age for group A was 32.8 years & group B was 27.7 years. The most affected group was 18-31 years for both groups. The sex distribution in our study sample among 20 patients, the number of male

patient=14 (70%) and Female=07 (30%). Main cause of fracture is Road traffic accident (RTA) that accounts 55% of all patient.

Table 1 showed the results of clinical findings. On Cross tabulation of peroperative stability between two groups, it was found that the intra operatively stability was obtained in all the cases except one case in group II. Peroperative stability of fractured segments between two groups is statistically insignificant as the p value is > 0.05. p-value measured by Chi-square test. Maximum mouth opening was gradually increasing in all cases of both groups. But there is no statistically significant differences between two groups (p-value measured by Unpaired t-test). Regarding occlusion, all cases had satisfactory occlusion intra-operatively. One case (5%) in group I had mild occlusal discrepancy in 1st week. Two cases (10%) in group II had mild occlusal discrepancy in 1st week post-operatively. The result is insignificant. p-value measured by Chi-square test.

The mean operation time from incision to wound closure was 43.55 min for group I and 55.65 min for group II. Statistical t-test was applied to compare both the groups and the results were statistically significant as p < 0.05. p-value measured by Unpaired t-test.

Table 2 showed the radiographic findings. It was found that all patients had precise anatomical reduction of fracture fragments on 1st week post-operatively except one patient in group I and two patients in group II had slight displacement. But the result is Insignificant as p > 0.05. At 3rd month 15 cases in group I & 14 cases in group II had bony union. Four cases in group I & five cases in group II showed osteogenesis, The result is insignificant. p-value measured by Chi-square test.

Table 1. Results of clinical findings

Variables	Group 1 (n=20)	Group 2 (n=20)	p value
Preoperative stability			
Adequate	20	19	0.311
Inadequate	0	1	
Maximum mouth opening			
Preoperative	27.3± 2.46	27.7±2.19	0.590
Intra-operative	35.5±4.61	34.9±3.42	0.643
1 st week postoperative	26.7±3.57	26.2±2.87	0.628
1 month postoperative	32.4±2.96	31.3±4.13	1.000
3 rd month postoperative	34.5±2.39	34.1±6.58	0.799
Cross tabulation of Occlusion			
At 1st week			
Occlusion present	19(95.0%)	18(90.0%)	
Deranged occlusion	0	0	
Mild discrepancy	1(5.0%)	2(10.0%)	
At 1st months			
Occlusion present	20(100%)	20(100%)	
Deranged occlusion	0	0	

Mild discrepancy	0(0%)	0(0%)	
At 3rd months			
Occlusion present	20(100%)	20(100%)	
Deranged occlusion	0	0	
Mild discrepancy	0(0%)	0(0%)	
Sensory disturbance			
At 1st week			
Present	1	2	0.548
Absent	19	18	
At 3 months			
Present	1	2	
Absent	19	18	0.548
Operative time			
	43.55±2.33	55.65±2.64	<0.001

Table 2. Results of radiological findings

Variables	Group 1(n=20)	Group 2 (n=20)	p value
Accuracy of reduction			
At 1st week			
Precise anatomical reduction	19	18	0.528
Slightly displaced	1	2	
Poorly reduced fracture	0	0	
At 1st month			
Precise anatomical reduction	20	20	
Slightly displaced	0	0	
Poorly reduced fracture	0	0	
Assessment of bone healing at 3 months			
Unchanged	0	0	
Localized periosteal reaction	3	4	0.727
Osteogenesis	4	5	0.763
Union	15	14	0.887

miniplate fixation in anterior mandibular fracture by Khairi *et al.*⁴ Among them 6 patients were male and 1 patient was female. These finding is consistence with the previous studies conducted all over the world.¹⁵⁻¹⁷

Regarding the etiology of mandibular fractures in this study, Road traffic accidents were the main etiologic factor representing 55% of cases in group I and 60% in group II and this was found to be in agreement with Khairi *et al.*⁴ (2016), Subhashraj *et al.*¹⁸ and Sakr *et al.*¹⁹ who supporting reported Road traffic accidents around 39% to 70% fracture of the mandible. On the other hand, other Shreya Verma and Ian Chambers found assault main etiologic factor representing 61% where as in our study Physical assault Accounts 25% of All Cases. In Bangladesh, the major cause of mandibular fracture is Road traffic accident (58.4%) The other causes are Fall from height, sports, abuse & so on.^{2,5,6}

In this study Intra-operatively stability was obtained in all 20 (100%) cases of group I (double Y) and group II (Champy's plate) after fixation. On 2nd week post operatively mobility (due to infected tooth in fracture line) was noted in one case(10%) of both group, which was treated by extraction of tooth & MMF for a period of 3 weeks. 6 weeks post operatively stability was found in all 20 (100%) cases. There is no statistically significant difference among two groups. This findings correlate with the study of Khairi *et al.*⁴ 2016.

In this study Maximum mouth opening was significantly increased in all cases across the follow up period where mean maximum mouth opening after 24 hours, one week, one month and three months follow up period were found to be statistically significant as p value were <0.001 (p < 0.05) for both groups.

One of the most important goal of mandibular fracture repair is the restoration of the pre-injury occlusion. Before any hardware is applied, the occlusion must be established with maxillomandibular fixation.²⁰ In this study in every case prior to Double Y miniplate and Champy's miniplate fixation proper occlusion was obtained. The occlusion of patient was checked postoperatively at regular intervals in 1 week, 1 month and 3 months.

In case of double Y shaped miniplate we encountered with one (5%) cases of occlusal discrepancy. In this case mild occlusal discrepancy was noted on 1st day post operatively which was treated by maxillomandibular fixation for 3 weeks. On 2nd month occlusion was found satisfactory for all these patients. This was in disagreement with Ellis *et al* who stated that because the second fracture changes the biomechanics acting across the fractures, it is possible that single titanium miniplates applied to both fractures cannot counter the more complex forces working on the dentosseous fragment between the 2 fractures. On the other hand out of 20, 18 patients of Champy's miniplate osteosynthesis had normal postoperative occlusion. Two patients had mild occlusal discrepancy which was corrected by MMF & simple selective occlusal grinding. This incidence of occlusal discrepancy was compared between two groups and the result showed no statistically significant. After 2 months of follow up period all cases of both groups had satisfactory occlusion. So, in a matter of postoperative occlusion between double Y shaped miniplate and Champy's miniplate was statistically insignificant.

There are several different factors that may result in sensory disturbances. Nerve injury can be caused by the trauma, but also by the treatment. During the operative procedure, the nerve may be involved in traction and/ compression. Manipulation of fragments during reduction and stabilization of the fracture or extraction of a third molar also could cause injury to the inferior alveolar nerve.²¹ In this study No sensory disturbances were reported in any case except for 1 case in Group I and 2 cases in Group II that developed mental nerve concussion. These patients had complained of lower lip paresthesia 1st week postoperatively. Patient was treated with vitamin B complex postoperatively for one month. Three months post operatively none of the patients had any signs of mental nerve injury. It may be due to mental nerve compression or traction per operatively.

The time taken for fixation directly reflects the difficulty in placement of a particular plate. The time of mini plates fixation is calculated from the beginning of plate adaptation to placement of the last screw. Various surgeons have reported reduced operating time with the usage of a single plate. As the double Y shaped mini plate is a single plate, less screws are used in fixation (6 screws) compared to using two conventional plates which will consume between 8 to 10 screws, hence increasing the time spent to adapt the plates and complete fixation. It can be assumed that the easier application of 3D single plates was reflected in a reduced average operating time. The time taken for double Y- shaped plate adaptation to definitive fixation in this study ranged from 10 to 12 min. It was a significantly faster fixation time compared to conventional mini plates used in the study.⁴

In this study the mean operative time for double Y shaped miniplate was 45.01 minutes. In case of Champy's double miniplate it was 58.05 min. Statistical analysis was done to compare the mean operative time between the two groups and the result was Statistically significant for group I. Easy application, simplified adaptation to the bone as well as simultaneous stabilization at both the superior and inferior borders, few number of screw and single plate was used, make the double Y shaped miniplate a time saving alternative to conventional double miniplate. These findings are also similar to the study of Khairi et al. ⁴2016 and some study about single 3D plate application in mandibular fracture.²²⁻²⁴

Immediate postoperative orthopantomogram showed satisfactory reduction in all cases except one patient in group I and two patients in group II had slight displacement. After one month, the panoramic views showed stable fracture segments in all cases. After three months, the panoramic views showed 15 cases in group I & 14 cases in group II had bony union. Four case in group I & five cases in group II showed osteogenesis, 3 cases in group I & 4 cases in group II showed localized periosteal reaction.

Besides the many advantages that fixation of mandibular fractures offer, the use of double Y shaped miniplate fixation has many unique advantages over conventional miniplate fixation. The major advantage is it can be applied more rapidly, since the time consuming task of adapting two miniplate is eliminated. Double Y shaped miniplate achieves maximum stability with minimum of implant material.

Therefore, through this study we realized that, the technique of double Y miniplate fixation is quite practicable in managing anterior mandibular fractures for surgeons. It provides effective internal fixation. However it is felt that a study of larger sample and longer follow up is required to show the reliability of double Y shaped miniplate fixation for anterior mandibular fractures.

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